

FORCES AND MEANS OF ENSURING THE MILITARY SECURITY OF THE STATE

Kilichov Normumin Nazarovich

Associate Professor,

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Abstract. This article analyzes the forces and means of ensuring state military security based on an institutional and functional approach. The author reveals national security resources through the role of state power structures, national capacity criteria, and civil society institutions. The article scientifically studies external and international legal means of ensuring military security, in particular, the collective security system based on the UN Charter, confidence-building measures within the OSCE and SCO, and the regime of nuclear-free zones (including the experience of Central Asia), which is considered a factor of global stability.

Keywords: Forces and means, Armed Forces, specially authorized bodies, strong society, collective security, confidence-building measures, SCO agreements, nuclear-free zone, Semipalatinsk Treaty, imperative norms.

The defense potential of a state is determined not only by the number of its direct military units, but also by a multifaceted combination of material, moral, institutional and international legal means serving this purpose. In the context of modern asymmetric and hybrid threats, the concept of military security goes beyond traditional military limitations and requires the integration of fundamental science, demography and international diplomatic institutions. This study systematically analyzes the hierarchy of internal forces and means of state military security, as well as international legal mechanisms that stabilize global and regional security.

Another important component of the national security system is the forces and means. The force includes the armed forces of the state and its components, specially authorized bodies of the state (intelligence, anti-terrorist structures). The means of ensuring national security can include the legal, organizational, technical, technological and other capabilities of the state [1].

In this regard, such aspects as the state's military, industrial and fundamental science potential, the effectiveness of the education system, the correspondence of the demographic situation to the development of society and the state, the state of ethnic and interreligious relations play an important role in creating the appropriate forces and means.

The second group of means is the "non-state" or civil society institution. One of the most strategic goals that Uzbekistan has set for itself is the transition from a strong state to a strong society. This, in turn, requires increasing the role of public organizations and associations, as well as the individual in the governance of the state and society, along with the role of state agencies. Today, more than 11 thousand non-governmental non-profit organizations operate in the Republic of Uzbekistan. These institutions are reliable and effective means of realizing the interests of the individual/human and society, two fundamental subjects of national security.

The armed forces are the regular military units of the state. Regular armed forces are created by the state and are maintained by the state in order to protect the sovereignty, territorial integrity and constitutional order of the state from external military threats.

International legal instruments are also important in ensuring national security. International legal instruments include generally recognized norms and principles of international law; universal and regional collective security systems; confidence-building measures; peacekeeping forces; disarmament; non-alignment and neutrality, etc.

The fundamental principles of international law are general norms that determine the essence and specific aspects of international law and have the highest political, legal and moral authority. They constitute the foundation of general international law and serve as the main criterion for determining the legality of the activities of subjects of international law. The fundamental principles of international law are universal, universally recognized and universally binding norms. Therefore, they are accepted by the international community as a whole. They are imperative norms of international law, from which any deviation is prohibited.

The fundamental principles of international law are mainly reflected in the following international legal instruments: the UN Charter, the Declaration on Principles of International Law (1970), and the Final Act of the OSCE (1975).

The basic principles of international law include: the threat or use of force, the peaceful settlement of international disputes, non-interference in the internal affairs of states, the right of peoples to self-determination, sovereign equality, the conscientious fulfillment of obligations assumed under international law, cooperation (in the UN Charter and the Declaration), respect for human rights, territorial integrity and inviolability of borders.

Collective security is a system of joint measures of states to ensure and restore international peace and security, established in the UN Charter and implemented within the framework of universal and regional organizations. The essence of the concept of collective security is that the security dilemma of states is resolved not by individual states or the balance of power, but through the institution of collective obligations. Collective security is based on the principle of "one for all - all for one". Measures within the framework of collective security are directed against a member of this organization that violates the rules of coexistence and existence.

Confidence-building measures are special measures aimed at eliminating mutual distrust and deterioration of relations due to misunderstandings/ disagreements in the military sphere. Confidence-building measures are a relatively new element of the general system of collective security. The current system of confidence-building measures is primarily enshrined in the documents of the CSCE. In the Final Act of the CSCE (1975), the member states agreed to notify each other in advance of: all large-scale military exercises of ground forces; movements of large numbers of troops; exchange of observers at military exercises. The system of organizational and legal measures aimed at reducing military risks and ensuring confidence-building measures in Central Asia was reflected in the main documents of the SCO (the Treaties on Strengthening Confidence-Building in the Military Sphere in the Border Area (1996) and on Mutual Reduction of Armed Forces in the Border Area (1997)).

A nuclear-free zone is an international legal regime that, based on a special international treaty, absolutely prohibits the development, testing, acquisition, and deployment of nuclear

weapons in a specific geographical area. Today, there are officially six strategic nuclear-free zones on our planet:

No	Nuclear-free zone (zone)	International treaty / document	On which it is based Year of adoption
1	Antarctica	International Treaty on Antarctica	1959
2	Africa	UN General Assembly Resolution / Treaty of Pelindaba	1961 / 1996
3	Latin America	Treaty of Tlatelolco (prohibition of nuclear weapons in Latin America)	1967
4	South Pacific Ocean	Treaty of Rarotonga	1985
5	Southeast Asia	Treaty of Bangkok	1995
6	Central Asia	Treaty of Semipalatinsk (nuclear-weapon-free zone in Central Asia)	2006

In conclusion, the military security of the state relies not only on the combat readiness of the regular Armed Forces and special services (forces), but also on the total potential of national resources, from fundamental science to more than 11 thousand civil society institutions (means).

In the international arena, the security of the Republic of Uzbekistan is legally guaranteed by the imperative principles of the UN Charter, the border confidence-building measures of 1996-1997 within the framework of the SCO, and the 2006 Treaty on the Central Asian Nuclear-Free Zone (Semipalatinsk), which is a geostrategic achievement for our region.

In its foreign policy, the new Uzbekistan, adhering to the principles of non-participation in military-political blocs and neutrality, demonstrates the most optimal model of ensuring both regional and national stability through the effective use of the institutions of indivisibility of security and collective obligations, which meets the requirements of the multipolar world..

List of used literature:

1. Defense Doctrine of the Republic of Uzbekistan. – T.: Uzbekistan, 2018., - P.6-9.
2. Odiljon, G. (2021). Stages of combating corruption in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Middle European Scientific Bulletin, 8, 270-274..

